

Characterization of Stratified Hydrogen Flames: Implications for Burner Design

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Abstract

To ensure efficient and safe combustion of hydrogen, novel burner designs are required. Additive Manufacturing enables the fabrication of complex geometries that can be leveraged to develop compact hydrogen burners. To meet various power demands, array configurations of multiple nozzles offer a promising route toward scalable and flexible combustors that can be tailored to specific applications. However, the design of additively manufactured burners for operation with hydrogen poses unique challenges due to the intricate interplay of fluid dynamic, thermal, and manufacturing constraints. This work investigates two additively manufactured nozzle designs that differ in the partially premixed mixture at their nozzle outlet. Their performance is analyzed under fuel lean conditions across a range of power outputs using experimental measurements and numerical simulations, leveraging the complementary strengths of each approach. The simulations provide detailed insights into internal mixing processes that are difficult to observe otherwise. Both experiments and simulations are used to examine flame morphologies. Flashback limits are determined experimentally, revealing notable differences between the two burner designs. A detailed numerical analysis of the mechanisms driving these differences is carried out and based on the findings we draw conclusions for the design of additively manufactured burners.

Novelty and significance statement

The novelty of this study stems from the joint experimental and numerical analysis of additively manufactured burners for partially premixed hydrogen-air flames, which specifically considers power modulation, flame stability and the flashback propensity of the flames. Previous works indicated the effectiveness of a radial mixture stratification to counteract the flashback propensity of burner-stabilized hydrogen flames. For the first time, this principle is experimentally tested using two additively manufactured nozzles. The flashback limits are determined, and the overall flame stability is analyzed revealing unexpected differences between the investigated designs. Based on the findings, we draw conclusions to guide future efforts for developing flashback-safe additively manufactured burners and enable multi-nozzle configurations.

Keywords: Partially Premixed Hydrogen Flames; Mixture Stratification; Flashback; Burner Design; Additive Manufacturing

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1. Introduction

Additive Manufacturing (AM) enables the construction of innovative and complex burner geometries. The broad design flexibility offered by AM holds great promise for addressing the burner design challenges arising from the unique combustion characteristics of hydrogen. One promising approach is the use of array configurations comprising many small flames, for instance as used in micromix combustion [11]. Arranging multiple burner elements in an array (e.g., [7, 10, 18, 26, 39]) offers similar advantages for developing compact and flexible burner designs, as individual nozzles can be easily added or removed to adjust the thermal power output. This modularity further ensures excellent scalability to meet the specific power requirements of different applications (e.g. as demonstrated in [39] for up to 10 MW thermal power output). In this context, previous works have successfully presented construction and operation of additively manufactured burner arrays and components [9, 12, 22]. Rajasegar, Choi, and co-workers introduced and characterized an additively manufactured burner array operating with swirl-stabilized bluff body flames [5, 6, 25, 26]. Durocher et al. [10] investigated an array of AM nozzles stabilizing hybrid micromix / premixed flames. As highlighted in their study, the interdisciplinary design approach, combining combustion science with AM, can present considerable challenges: The flashback limits showed a high sensitivity to manufacturing tolerances and surface roughness resulting from the AM process. This indicates that despite the design freedom offered by AM, research is required to identify burner design principles that effectively leverage the capabilities of AM techniques and offer efficient and safe combustion of hydrogen.

In the present work, two additively manufactured burner designs that are envisioned to be mounted in multi-nozzle arrangements are presented and characterized. The designs are scrutinized with respect to their capabilities to modulate the thermal power output through numerical simulations and experiments, determining the limits of stable operation. Indicators for the flashback modes of the two designs are derived, revealing notable differences. The first burner design is based on the work of Schmidt et al. [29], who characterized the partially premixed burner with respect to NO_x emissions at power outputs ranging from 0.6 kW to 1.2 kW and at different equivalence ratios. The second burner is designed to produce a radially stratified mixture. Following the work by Vance, Scholtissek et al. [33, 35], the burner features lean mixtures in vicinity of the nozzle wall, reducing the local flame speed in the boundary layer and thereby mitigating the risk of boundary layer flashback. This concept is now for the first time experimentally tested. Building on the flashback regime characterization by Ali and Bastiaans [1], who identified distinct regimes based on the flame shape during flashback and showed that a Soret-induced mixture

stratification can alter the flashback regime for nozzles of different diameters, the present work derives indicators for the observed flashback regime under the external mixture stratification of the investigated nozzle designs. These indicators are based on high-speed recordings of the flashback process and numerical analysis of the mixture fields.

The objectives of this study are threefold: *First*, we aim to characterize the partially premixed, additively manufactured burner nozzles at various thermal power outputs under lean conditions. This includes a detailed assessment of the mean and fluctuating mixture fields, the flame morphology, and the location of the main reaction zone through a combined experimental/numerical analysis. *Second*, the flashback limits of the investigated designs are experimentally determined, and the indicators for the flashback mode, characterized as boundary layer or core flow flashback, are identified. *Third*, the sensitivity of the designs to geometric tolerances is assessed to gain insights for the development of robust designs for industrial applications.

Based on these analyses, we draw conclusions for the design of additively manufactured nozzles to ensure safe, efficient, and robust burner operation.

2. Methods

The two burner designs are presented in Fig. 1. Both nozzles have been additively manufactured from 1.4404 stainless steel using a PBF-LB/M machine type AconityMINI with a layer thickness of 30 μm . Design (a) is the reference nozzle design by Schmidt et al. [29]. Design (b) is optimized to produce a radially stratified mixture with leaner than average mixtures in vicinity of the nozzle wall following [35]. Both designs feature two concentric pipes with a converging nozzle. The central pipe supplies pure hydrogen, while air is supplied in the surrounding annulus. The hydrogen stream exits through holes in the central pipe and is forced around a plate-shaped flow body before entering a short premixing section. This small premixing section minimizes the effect of flashback on the burner nozzle and allows for experimental determination of the flashback limits. The flames are expected to stabilize at the nozzle outlet. The most notable difference between the two designs is the size of the holes through which hydrogen is injected into the air flow, significantly altering the fuel-air mixing characteristics, as will be shown below. The burners are operated under ambient temperature and pressure at a constant global equivalence ratio, $\phi_g = 0.6$. The investigated power outputs range from the respective flashback limit up to 1.8 kW. This results in a weakly turbulent flow with Reynolds numbers at the outlet of up to $Re \approx 8100$.

2.1. Experimental Setup

The flame morphology and stability are visualized using 5000 high-speed OH* chemiluminescence images which are taken at 38 kHz with an intensified

Fig. 1: Mixture distribution at the outlets of the nozzles. Design (a) is the design by Schmidt et al. [29] and design (b) is an optimized design. On the left, the time-averaged local equivalence ratio is presented. Fluctuations in the mixture are quantified with the standard deviation of the H_2 mass fraction on the right.

Phantom v2012 CMOS camera. A filter centered at 308 nm with a bandwidth of 50 nm ensures that the detection is limited to the chemiluminescence emissions of excited OH^* radicals. To determine the thermal load on the nozzle, simultaneous IR-thermometry is performed using an *Optris Xi400* IR-camera. To obtain accurate wall temperatures of the nozzle, the known emission coefficients of 0.95 of white polyimide IR-stickers are used to determine the temperature over 3 different positions on the nozzle rim. These temperatures are averaged to eliminate potential influences of the viewing-angle. The resulting temperatures are then used as boundary conditions for the simulations. To analyze the stability of the flames, the flashback limits are first determined for each nozzle. Holding ϕ_g constant using *Bronkhorst Mass Flow Controllers*, the power output is gradually decreased until flashback occurs. Based on the flashback limits, a stable operating regime is identified starting at 0.6 kW. Within this regime, additional measurements are taken in 0.2 kW increments up to 1.8 kW.

2.2. Numerical Setup

Simulations of the two nozzle designs are carried out at three power outputs: 0.8 kW, 1 kW, and 1.2 kW. The OpenFOAM framework [37] is utilized with an in-house solver that is coupled to the library Cantera [13] for the calculation of thermodynamic and transport properties. The computation of the chemical reactions is dynamically load balanced [23]. The reactions are computed using a reduced kinetic model by Li et al. [20] and diffusion is modeled using a mixture-averaged model [16] including Soret diffusion [28]. A load balanced adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) library [14, 27] is used to refine the mesh around the flame front by one level of refinement. As in our previous work [33], two simulations are conducted per nozzle design and operating point: First, the internal mixture formation is simulated in non-reactive precursor simulations. The results 5 mm upstream of the nozzle outlet are then mapped to the reactive domain. The domain used for the reactive simulations is larger than that of comparable studies [33, 38] measuring 55 mm in length and 30 mm

in diameter. The chosen mesh resolution in all domains is sufficiently high to resolve the near-wall flow structures ($y^+ < 5$ across all power outputs) and the energy-containing turbulent structures. The effect of unresolved subgrid-scale turbulent motions is modeled using the σ -model by Nicoud et al. [24]. The Artificially Thickened Flame (ATF) model is used to model turbulence-chemistry interactions and to lower spatial resolution requirements [3]. Dynamic thickening is applied to place at least 12 cells in the flame front. A flame sensor based on the H_2O mass fraction, used as a combustion progress variable, limits the thickening to the flame front region. The same sensor is used for adaptive mesh refinement. To model the effect of subfilter scale fluctuations on the flame, the efficiency function by Charlette et al. [4] is applied. Lean H_2 flames are prone to thermo-diffusive instabilities, which significantly increase their flame speed [2, 15, 17, 21]. Artificial flame thickening alters the relevant flame length scales, thereby affecting the nonlinear instability characteristics and, consequently, the consumption speed. To account for these modified flame dynamics, the efficiency function proposed by Schuh et al. [30, 31] is applied.

Local and non-dimensional input variables to the ATF model and the efficiency functions, such as the local flame thickness, flame speed, and effective Lewis number, among others, are tabulated and accessed based on the local mixture fraction to account for the effect of the mixture stratification.

The inlets to the domain remain laminar for all operating points: in the central H_2 pipe, the Reynolds number is $Re_{H_2} < 500$ and in the annular air flow the Reynolds number is $Re_{air} < 1550$ across all simulated power outputs. Hence, analytical laminar velocity profiles for the Poiseuille flows in the pipe and the surrounding annulus are prescribed. Turbulence is generated from the interaction of the flow with internal geometric features. The wall temperature is fixed to the experimentally measured nozzle temperatures. Zero diffusive flux across the domain boundaries is ensured using a Robin boundary condition as presented in [32].

3. Mixture Characterization

To better understand the characteristics of the flames anchored to the two burner designs, the partially premixed mixtures at the nozzle outlet planes are analyzed first. The local mixtures (as obtained from LES) are presented in Fig. 1. For each simulated power output, the local equivalence ratio, averaged over time, is indicated. Although the two burner designs have a very similar internal geometry, large differences in the mixture formation are observed. For design (a), richer-than-average regions are observed near the nozzle wall. These locally richer mixture are distributed in six zones along the circumference of the nozzle, coinciding with the locations of the holes in the central H_2 tube. Toward the center of nozzle (a), the mixture is slightly leaner than the specified global equivalence ratio. In contrast, design (b) exhibits a radially stratified mixture with leaner mixtures at the nozzle wall and richer mixtures toward the center with local equivalence ratios up to $\phi = 1.2$. It has been shown by Vance and Scholtissek [35] that such a radial mixture stratification locally reduces the flame speed in the boundary layer, consequently reducing the propensity to flame flashback while maintaining similar power outputs. Prior work has indicated the effectiveness of this approach also in a weakly turbulent regime [33]. Design (b) is the result of a shape optimization process aiming to produce this radial mixture stratification in real burner nozzle geometries.

When comparing the mixtures at different power outputs, increased spatial mixture variations with increasing power are apparent. This indicates that turbulence-enhanced mixing insufficiently compensates for the shorter residence times in the premixing section due to the increased bulk velocity.

The resolved fluctuations in the mixture field are quantified using the local standard deviation of the H_2 mass fraction, $\sigma(Y_{H_2})$. This is indicated on the right in Fig. 1. Overall, the magnitudes of the fluctuations are similar for both designs, however, they are distributed differently. Design (b) exhibits lower near-wall fluctuations compared to the reference design (a) but produces larger variations toward the center of the nozzle. A similar pattern can be observed for the fluctuations in the flow velocity (not shown here).

4. Flame Characterization

The flames that stabilize at the two burners are first characterized by analyzing their shape and the location of the main reaction zone. To this end, the line-of-sight integrated, time-averaged heat release rate is evaluated from LES across the different power outputs. For the lack of a better experimental marker for the heat release zones in pure H_2 -air flames, the simulation results are qualitatively compared to time-averaged OH^* chemiluminescence images.

Fig. 2: OH^* chemiluminescence measurements, averaged over 5000 frames. The flames stabilized on nozzle design (a) are presented in the top row, while the flames on design (b) are presented in the bottom row. Asymmetric flames are observed for both burner designs across all investigated power outputs.

Fig. 3: Numerical results for the line-of-sight integrated heat release rate, averaged over time. The figure shows symmetric flames which are obtained from the simulations assuming ideal burner geometries.

4.1. Morphology

The time-averaged OH^* chemiluminescence measurements of the flames that are established on the two burner designs are presented in Fig. 2, operating at $P_{th} = 0.8$ kW, $P_{th} = 1.0$ kW, and $P_{th} = 1.2$ kW. The time-averaged heat release rate obtained from the simulations is presented in Fig. 3. It is line-of-sight integrated to qualitatively mimic the experimental OH^* measurements. While this approach does not permit a quantitative comparison between numerical and experimental results, both reveal insights into the flame morphology, its approximate size, and the locations of highest reactivity.

In the experiments, slightly asymmetric flames are established for all operating conditions and nozzle designs (cf. Sec 4.3). The flames exhibit a preferential anchoring to the right side. Differences in the flame

shape and the location of the main reaction zone are apparent between the two nozzle designs. While the location of highest reactivity appears to be distributed evenly over the flame length for design (a), elevated heat release is observed toward the flame tip for design (b). Along the nozzle’s circumference, however, the main reaction zones are observed to be concentrated in distinct zones, leading to a striped pattern for design (a), while the chemiluminescence intensity is more evenly distributed along the circumference for design (b). This observation aligns with the pattern in the mixture distribution at the outlets of the nozzles (cf. Fig. 1), with locally richer mixtures being distributed along the circumference for design (a).

In contrast to the asymmetric flames observed in the experiments, symmetric flames are obtained in the simulations under the assumption of ideal conditions and surfaces. While the flames established with design (a) feature a conical shape with a tapered tip, the flames of design (b) exhibit a rather cylindrical shape with a rounded tip. This is a result of the radial mixture stratification and agrees with the findings of our prior work [33]. An elevated heat release rate is observed at the flame base with weaker burning toward the flame tip for design (a), which is not as clearly visible in the experimental data. However, the enhanced burning toward the flame tip and reduced burning near the flame base for design (b) is observed in both the experimental and numerical data. This observation is attributed to the local mixture distribution at the nozzle outlet: Design (a) exhibits mixtures closer to stoichiometry toward the nozzle wall, while the fuel is concentrated toward the nozzle center of design (b) (cf. Fig. 1). When comparing the flame lengths from the simulations to the experimental measurements, the simulated flames appear slightly longer across all operating points and burner designs, which is attributed to the differences in flame symmetry and flame shape, most notably the tapered flame tip in the simulations. Furthermore, slight preheating due to elevated nozzle temperatures could influence the flame length, which is not captured in the simulations since ambient temperature is prescribed at the inlets to the reactive domain. While stable flames are established for all presented power outputs in the experiments, blow-off is observed for design (b) at a power output of 1.2 kW. This aspect is analyzed in greater detail in Sec. 4.2. The observed differences in the flame symmetry and the location of the main reaction zones indicate that the spatial mixture distribution that develops assuming ideal geometries and inflow conditions in the simulations does not exactly match the local mixture distribution in the experiments. The asymmetric flame shapes suggest that these differences originate from a small misalignment between flow body and nozzle, caused by manufacturing and mounting tolerances. The sensitivity of the mixture formation on the tolerances is therefore analyzed in Sec. 4.3.

The lower heat release at the flame base for nozzle (b) is also observed in the nozzle temperature mea-

surements. While overall low nozzle temperatures are measured (maximum nozzle temperature $t_{\max} = 77.3^\circ\text{C}$), the temperature of nozzle (b) remains consistently lower than that of nozzle (a) for each power output. This is an effect of the radial mixture stratification and confirms the findings of the numerical studies in [33] and [35], in which lower wall heat fluxes are reported for radially stratified flames.

4.2. Flame Stability

The flashback limits are experimentally determined for both nozzle designs. High-speed OH* chemiluminescence recordings of the flashback process in both nozzle designs are presented in Fig. 4. Although design (b) was optimized to reduce the propensity to boundary layer flashback, surprisingly, flashback is observed at $P_{\text{th}} = 0.3$ kW for design (a), while for design (b) flashback already occurs at $P_{\text{th}} = 0.45$ kW. To better understand this unexpected behavior, the flashback mode is analyzed. For design (a), flashback seems to originate from the flame base on the left side. A flame zone of enhanced OH* chemiluminescence intensity is observed to approach the nozzle outlet before disappearing inside the nozzle. Although the line-of-sight integrated nature of the recordings precludes definitive conclusions regarding the flashback mode, the recordings suggest boundary layer flashback to be the governing mechanism for design (a).

Design (b) exhibits an initially asymmetrically anchored flame with elevated burning toward the flame tip, from which a flame front propagates toward the nozzle outlet and disappears inside. The remaining flame appears to follow this propagating front into the nozzle. These observations suggest that the flame front propagates through the core flow at the center of the nozzle outlet, indicating core flow flashback as the governing mechanism.

To further analyze the flashback mode, these observations are compared to the velocity field and the local mixture field from the simulations. As a marker for the propensity to core flow flashback, the laminar burning velocity, s_L , from 1D freely propagating flames corresponding to the respective local mixture is related to the axial velocity at that same location. The propensity to boundary layer flashback is estimated using the radial velocity gradient, $\partial_r U_{\text{ax}}$, following the critical gradient theory for boundary layer flashback by Lewis and von Elbe [19, 36]. To account for the local mixture stratification, the velocity gradient is normalized with the laminar burning velocity divided by the laminar flame thickness, s_L/δ_F following the critical gradient definition in [1]. Although this estimation neglects flame stretch effects, which are considered in [34], the qualitative conclusions regarding boundary layer flashback propensity are not expected to be affected as both flames are subjected to comparable external stretch rates at identical power output. For this analysis, the mean fields from

Fig. 4: High-speed OH* chemiluminescence recordings of flashback occurring for designs (a) (top row) and (b) (bottom row).

the simulations at 0.8 kW are used. The results are presented in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Estimation of the propensity to core flow flashback (left), and to boundary layer flashback (right) using time-averaged data from LES at 0.8 kW power output.

While the s_L/U_{ax} ratio is reduced toward the center of nozzle (a) and higher toward the nozzle wall, design (b) exhibits higher s_L/U_{ax} ratios in the core flow. This suggests a higher propensity to core flow flashback in design (b). Analysis of the near-wall velocity gradient reveals a lower gradient at the wall of nozzle design (a) and a higher gradient for nozzle design (b). This indicates a higher propensity to boundary layer flashback in design (a) compared to design (b). The propensity to boundary layer flashback is further reduced in design (b) by the targeted radial mixture stratification, which locally reduces the flame speed in the boundary layer. It is emphasized that this analysis considers the mean fields. The local mixture fluctuations that are presented in Fig. 1 reveal increased fluctuations toward the nozzle wall of design (a) while more fluctuations are observed away from the wall at the mixture interface in design (b). It is assumed that these near-wall mixture fluctuations in design (a) further increase the likelihood of boundary layer flashback triggered by a mixture fluctuation toward fuel-rich conditions. These indicators support

the hypotheses about the flashback modes based on the observation of the high-speed flashback recordings.

When increasing the thermal power output in the experiments, the flames remain anchored up to $P_{th} = 1.8$ kW. In the simulations of design (b), however, blow-off is observed at $P_{th} = 1.2$ kW power output. This is attributed to an increasing mixture stratification with increasing power outputs: The increasingly leaner mixtures in vicinity of the nozzle wall of design (b), as presented in Fig. 1, weakens flame anchoring, which leads to an increased propensity to blow-off. At 1.2 kW power output, the mean equivalence ratio at the wall is $\langle \phi \rangle|_{r_{wall}} \approx 0.27$ and therefore approaching the lean extinction limit of strained H_2 -air flames [8]. This ultra-lean mixture, combined with increased strain through overall higher outlet velocities at higher power outputs leads to the observed blow-off. In the experimental investigation of the asymmetric flames, blow-off is observed only at higher power outputs and the flame remains anchored also at higher power outputs than 1.2 kW. The different blow-off limits suggest that asymmetries in the mixture field with locally richer mixtures have a stabilizing effect in the experimental investigation and lead to the observed asymmetric flame anchoring. To test this hypothesis and to investigate potential sources of these asymmetries, the sensitivity of the local mixture to flowbody–nozzle misalignment is assessed numerically.

4.3. Sensitivity on Mounting Tolerances

So far, the simulations assumed ideal geometries leading to the well-defined mixture patterns presented in Fig. 1. However, the mean OH* chemiluminescence measurements reveal asymmetries in all flames, suggesting slight deviations from the original design that are often inevitable in real burner setups. Therefore, the sensitivity of the nozzle designs on mounting tolerances is analyzed numerically. To this end, non-reactive LES of the internal mixing processes are conducted with slightly misaligned geometries: For

both designs, the flow body and the H₂-carrying pipe are shifted 0.5 mm off center, corresponding to a misalignment of only approx. 3 % of the diameter of the nozzle at the position of the flow body. These simulations are conducted at the same global equivalence ratio and at a power output close to flashback ($P_{th} = 0.6$ kW). The resulting local mixture field and the fluctuations are presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6: Mixture fields at nozzle outlet for misaligned flow bodies and nozzles by 0.5 mm.

For both nozzle designs, a significant asymmetry is introduced to the mixture field. Design (b) exhibits a section with locally richer mixtures at the nozzle wall. This coincides with large fluctuations resulting in instantaneous events with near stoichiometric mixtures close to the nozzle wall. Thus, already a slight off-center placement of the flow body in the nozzle would counteract the benefits of radially stratified mixtures that were shown in previous works [33, 35]. The locally richer mixtures in Fig. 6 further support the hypothesis that the asymmetries in the mixture field aid flame anchoring at higher power outputs, as blow-off is observed for design (b) at $P_{th} = 1.2$ kW in the simulations while the flame could be stabilized under these conditions in the experiments. Additionally, the preferential attachment of the flame to one side of the nozzle, most prominently visible for design (a) at high power outputs (see Fig. 2), can be explained by the asymmetric mixture field cause by a slight misalignment of flow body and nozzle.

To validate the assumptions about the interactions between misaligned geometries, local mixture distribution and flame stabilization, experiments are repeated for design (b), this time featuring an alignment fixture to ensure concentricity of flow body and nozzle. This assembly is presented together with the averaged OH* chemiluminescence measurements in Fig. 7. A significant improvement of the symmetry of the flames is observed. The shift of the location of the main reaction zone toward the flame tip is clearly visible, indicating that this concentric design succeeds in

Fig. 7: Symmetric flames observed in experiments for design (b) when concentricity of the flowbody inside the nozzle is enforced by an alignment fixture placed upstream.

producing the targeted radially stratified mixture. The flame length for the enhanced design (b) with concentric flow body remains slightly below the length observed in the simulations for the idealized design (b) (c.f. 7). This is attributed to an unknown amount of pre-heating of the fresh gas due to elevated nozzle temperatures that is not fully captured in the simulations. Although the enhanced concentric design leads to a more symmetric flame topology, the flashback limit remains identical to that of the asymmetric design, still occurring at $P_{th} = 0.45$ kW. This supports the interpretation that core flow flashback is the driving flashback mechanism in this configuration, as the design otherwise now succeeds in producing the radially stratified mixture that was shown to reduce the propensity to boundary layer flashback [35]. Blow-off is observed at a power output of $P_{th} = 1.2$ kW, now matching the blow-off limit in the simulations and confirming that asymmetries in the mixture field enhance flame anchoring.

5. Conclusions and Implications for Burner Design

Two partially premixed hydrogen burner designs intended for operation in multi-nozzle arrangements are investigated under lean operating conditions and across varying power outputs. While nozzle (a) exhibits richer-than-average mixtures toward the nozzle wall, nozzle (b) produces a stratified mixture with leaner mixtures near the nozzle wall. As a result, differences in flame shape, nozzle temperatures, and flame stability are observed. Despite the similarity of the nozzle geometries, our combined experimental and numerical study shows that even moderate internal nozzle modifications can significantly influence flame characteristics and burner performance. We provide experimental evidence that a local mixture stratification can have a leading-order effect on hydrogen flame stabilization. This underscores the great potential of nozzle shape optimization to construct de-

signs, leveraging additive manufacturing capabilities. At the same time, our results show that the optimization process must balance multiple criteria to avoid adverse effects. These include flashback propensity and mode, sensitivity to manufacturing and mounting tolerances, and mixture characteristics at different operating conditions. Based on our detailed numerical and experimental analyses, we draw the following conclusions for burner design:

1. **Mixture stratification can influence the dominant flashback mode.** Radial stratification can reduce the propensity to boundary-layer flashback in premixed hydrogen flames, but excessive stratification can promote core-flow flashback. The effect of mixture stratification on the flashback mode must therefore be considered during nozzle shape optimization.
2. **Power modulation affects mixture stratification with consequences for stability limits.** For the nozzles studied here, spatial mixture variations increase with increasing power output. Nozzles optimized for mixture stratification with lean near-wall mixtures close to flashback conditions can become more prone to blow-off at higher power outputs. Optimization targets should account for this by maintaining sufficient near-wall fuel content as power increases to support flame anchoring.
3. **Intrinsically concentric internal structures are required for robust manufacturing and operation.** Key mixing elements should be mechanically fixed or self-centering to minimize sensitivity to mounting tolerances. Additive manufacturing enables such integrated, concentric geometries (e.g., a fixed flow body as shown in Fig. 8) that are difficult to achieve with conventional manufacturing techniques.

Fig. 8: Intrinsically concentric burner design that has been investigated in [33].

In our future work we will study the performance and stability limits of designs similar to the one presented in Fig. 8. For this nozzle design, fuel-lean mixtures were reported both near the nozzle wall and at the nozzle center, with richer mixtures in between [33]. Such designs are therefore expected to significantly improve flame stability, enabling better use of AM capabilities to mitigate the flashback propensity of premixed hydrogen flames.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Raphael Strickling: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, software, validation, visualization, writing - original

draft. **Sebastian Faderl:** Data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, validation, visualization, writing - original draft. **Julian Schrauder:** investigation, methodology, writing - review and editing. **Faizan Habib Vance:** Conceptualization, supervision, writing - review and editing. **Florian J. Bauer:** Methodology, supervision, writing - review and editing. **Dominic Bartels:** Methodology, supervision, writing - review and editing. **Michael Schmidt:** Funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, writing - review and editing. **Stefan Will:** Funding acquisition, project administration, supervision, writing - review and editing. **Arne Scholtissek:** Conceptualization, funding acquisition, methodology, project administration, supervision, writing - review and editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Claude Sonnet 4.6 in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Data availability statement

The data presented in this study is available as supplementary material under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19036047>.

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